

Dichlorobarbituric Acid as an Oxidimetric Titrant : Direct Potentiometric and Visual Titrations in Aqueous Acetic Acid Medium

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A stable oxidimetric titrant 1,3-dichloro-5,5-diethylbarbituric acid (DCBA) in aqueous acetic acid is proposed for the direct potentiometric and visual titrations of a variety of simple and complex reductants. The reductants studied include antimony(III), iron(II), hexacyanoferrate(II), sulphite, ascorbic acid, hydroquinone, hydrazine, benzhydrazide, isoniazid, semicarbazide, thiourea, thiosemicarbazide and its metal complexes, thiocyanate, Reinecke's salt, mercury(II)tetrathiocyanatocobaltate(II), mercury(II)tetrathiocyanatozincate(II), aniline, phenol, oxine and metal oxinates, sulphanilic acid, anthranilic acid and metal anthranilates. The errors of the determinations vary from 0.2 to 0.4% for potentiometric titrations and 0.3 to 0.5% for visual titrations. The potentiometric methods are precise to 0.1–0.4% whereas the visual methods 0.1–0.3%.

THE chemistry of N-haloimides has attracted much attention as sources of halonium cations, hypohalite species and N-anions. They have also been used as powerful oxidants and halogenating agents in analytical and preparative organic chemistry. 1,3-Dichloro-5,5-diethylbarbituric acid (DCBA) has recently been exploited as a new oxidimetric titrant for the micro determination of certain metals¹. No systematic analytical work on DCBA has been attempted so far. Therefore as a part of our programme on redox titrants^{2,3}, we have investigated the efficacy of DCBA as an oxidimetric titrant. The solid sample and solutions of DCBA are relatively more stable than some of its analogues. DCBA has been successfully used as an oxidimetric titrant for the potentiometric and visual determination of 43 reductants in aqueous acetic acid medium.

Experimental

A Toshniwal CLO6A titration potentiometer with 'null meter' detector, a platinum indicator electrode, an aqueous saturated calomel reference electrode and other usual accessories were used for potentiometric titrations.

DCBA was prepared by the reported method¹. Its purity was checked by determining the active chlorine content (Found : Cl, 27.94. Required : Cl, 28.01%). DCBA is sparingly soluble in water but fairly soluble in acetic acid and other common organic solvents; it is quite stable upto a 15 days. Traces of water, light and heat accelerated the

deterioration and hence solutions were carefully stored in amber coloured bottles.

Solutions (~0.1 N) of all the reductants (Table 1) were prepared³ in appropriate solvents and the metal oxinates and anthranilates by standard methods³. Thiocyanate and thiosemicarbazide complexes were prepared by the reported methods^{4,5}. These complexes were dissolved in 2N HCl and diluted. In case of the complexes of lead, the precipitate formed was filtered off before dilution. These reductant solutions were standardised by standard methods^{3,6}.

Following aqueous indicator solutions were used for direct visual titrations: quinoline yellow (0.5%), amaranth (0.1%), methyl red (0.1%), methyl orange (0.1%) and *p*-ethoxy chrysoidine (0.1%).

Potentiometric method: To an aliquot (3–7 ml) of the reductant solution pipetted in a titration cell, potassium bromide (0.5 g) and other reagents such as sodium acetate or phosphoric acid etc if required, were added. The solution was diluted to 50 ml with 50% (v/v) aqueous acetic acid and titrated with DCBA. Near the equivalence point, the titrant was added in 0.1 ml portions, the solution stirred for 30 s and the steady potential noted. The titration was continued until there was no significant change in potential on further addition of the titrant. The equivalence point was calculated by the numerical methods⁷.

Visual method: Among the five indicators, the best indicator was selected by noting its colour

TABLE 1—TITRIMETRIC DETERMINATION OF THE REDUCTANTS AND METAL COMPLEXES

Compd.	No. of equivalents of DCBA consumed	Potentiometric titration			Visual titration		
		Amount taken mmol	Coefficient of variation %	Av. error*, %	Range studied mmol	Coefficient of variation %	Av. error**
Antimony(III)	2	0.142 8	0.05	± 0.12	0.58-1.20	0.11	± 0.10
Iron(II)	1	0.108 2	0.12	± 0.28	0.80-1.60	0.16	± 0.14
Hexacyanoferrate(II)	1	0.128 2	0.14	± 0.14	1.00-1.90	0.16	± 0.12
Sulphite	2	0.253 0	0.26	± 0.11	0.50-0.96	0.14	± 0.12
Ascorbic acid	2	0.182 5	0.07	± 0.32	0.37-0.72	0.22	± 0.18
Hydroquinone	2	0.119 1	0.06	± 0.20	0.40-0.77	0.26	± 0.21
Hydrazine	4	0.082 4	0.02	± 0.28	0.24-0.46	0.15	± 0.18
Benzhydrazide	4	0.078 2	0.25	± 0.40	0.24-0.47	0.21	± 0.17
Isoniazid	4	0.078 4	0.04	± 0.14	0.24-0.46	0.15	± 0.13
Semicarbazide	4	0.092 4	0.22	± 0.32	0.24-0.46	0.15	± 0.12
Thiourea	8	0.038 2	0.14	± 0.14	0.12-0.25	0.14	± 0.11
Thiosemicarbazide	10	0.038 2	0.18	± 0.28	0.09-0.18	0.13	± 0.11
Thiocyanate	6	0.048 2	0.14	± 0.12	0.13-0.26	0.18	± 0.14
Aniline	6	0.042 8	0.12	± 0.28	0.15-0.30	0.12	± 0.10
Phenol	6	0.048 2	0.14	± 0.11	0.15-0.29	0.08	± 0.07
Oxine	4	0.071 1	0.24	± 0.32	0.24-0.48	0.20	± 0.15
Sulphanilic acid	6	0.058 2	0.18	± 0.16	0.16-0.32	0.13	± 0.11
Anthranilic acid	6	0.048 2	0.18	± 0.14	0.17-0.34	0.17	± 0.15
Mn(C ₇ H ₆ O ₂ N) ₂	12	0.038 2	0.12	± 0.11	0.08-0.17	0.08	± 0.07
Co(C ₇ H ₆ O ₂ N) ₂	12	0.048 2	0.16	± 0.32	0.08-0.17	0.18	± 0.14
Ni(C ₇ H ₆ O ₂ N) ₂	12	0.034 8	0.14	± 0.12	0.07-0.15	0.10	± 0.08
Cu(C ₇ H ₆ O ₂ N) ₂	12	0.038 2	0.11	± 0.14	0.11-0.22	0.10	± 0.09
Zn(C ₇ H ₆ O ₂ N) ₂	12	0.049 0	0.29	± 0.11	0.08-0.16	0.22	± 0.16
Cd(C ₇ H ₆ O ₂ N) ₂	12	0.032 1	0.27	± 0.12	0.06-0.13	0.06	± 0.03
Pb(C ₇ H ₆ O ₂ N) ₂	12	0.038 7	0.25	± 0.34	0.08-0.18	0.11	± 0.09
Mg(C ₈ H ₈ ON) ₂	8	0.029 1	0.18	± 0.28	0.14-0.29	0.13	± 0.11
Ca(C ₈ H ₈ ON) ₂	8	0.041 1	0.24	± 0.11	0.13-0.27	0.10	± 0.09
Mn(C ₈ H ₈ ON) ₂	8	0.028 4	0.32	± 0.12	0.14-0.28	0.11	± 0.08
Co(C ₈ H ₈ ON) ₂	8	0.038 5	0.12	± 0.16	0.14-0.28	0.07	± 0.05
Ni(C ₈ H ₈ ON) ₂	8	0.048 2	0.33	± 0.14	0.13-0.26	0.20	± 0.15
Cu(C ₈ H ₈ ON) ₂	8	0.031 1	0.28	± 0.12	0.13-0.26	0.19	± 0.11
Cd(C ₈ H ₈ ON) ₂	8	0.036 4	0.24	± 0.22	0.09-0.19	0.14	± 0.10
La(C ₈ H ₈ ON) ₂	12	0.037 2	0.17	± 0.24	0.09-0.19	0.12	± 0.08
UO ₂ (C ₈ H ₈ ON) ₂ ·C ₈ H ₇ ON	12	0.029 1	0.21	± 0.28	0.09-0.18	0.11	± 0.10
Reineckel's salt	24	0.026 2	0.12	± 0.16	0.06-0.13	0.14	± 0.08
Hg[Co(CNS) ₄]	24	0.025 0	0.11	± 0.28	0.05-0.11	0.11	± 0.12
Hg[Zn(CNS) ₄]	24	0.026 0	0.10	± 0.18	0.04-0.10	0.10	± 0.11
Mn(CH ₄ N ₂ S) ₂	20	0.034 8	0.24	± 0.44	0.06-0.13	0.13	± 0.09
Ni(CH ₄ N ₂ S) ₂	20	0.029 1	0.28	± 0.40	0.03-0.08	0.19	± 0.15
Zn(CH ₄ N ₂ S) ₂	20	0.028 4	0.30	± 0.10	0.06-0.13	0.17	± 0.11
Cd(CH ₄ N ₂ S) ₂	20	0.025 4	0.11	± 0.38	0.05-0.10	0.16	± 0.10

*Six replicates. **Ten replicates.

change with potential in respective medium, i.e. with or without the auxiliary agents. The reductant solution was prepared in the same way as for potentiometric titration and the selected indicator was added. The DCBA solution was then added. A blank titration was done in each case and no blank correction was found necessary.

Results and Discussion

The results of the titrations are presented in Table 1. The half-cell reaction of DCBA is represented by

where RN₂Cl₂ stands for DCBA. The conditional redox potential of the couple [RN₂Cl₂]/[RN₂H₂] has been determined to be +1.21 V at 30° indicating that DCBA is a moderately strong oxidant.

The potential break in the potentiometric titration was sharp in the range 100-400 mV. The visual end-points were also sharp. Quinoline yellow was found to be the most suitable indicator for majority of the reductants. For iron(II), hexacyanoferrate(II) and metal oxinates and amaranth, methyl orange or methyl red were found to be most suitable. All the 43 reductants studied could be determined both by potentiometric and visual indicator methods. Addition of auxiliary agents was common for both the methods. Addition of potassium bromide (0.5 g) was essential for all the reductants. For iron(II), addition of orthophosphoric acid (2 ml) was essential. For isoniazid, thiourea, thiosemicarbazide, metal complexes of thiosemicarbazide, anthranilic acid and metal anthranilates, sodium acetate (0.5 g) was added which acted as a catalyst in these systems.

During the titration, antimony(III) was oxidised to +5 state, iron(II) and hexacyanoferrate to +3

state, ascorbic acid to dehydroascorbic acid and hydroquinone to quinone. Hydrazine and its derivatives were oxidised to molecular nitrogen; thiosemicarbazide to molecular nitrogen and sulphate; thiocyanate and thiourea to sulphate. Aniline, phenol, sulphanilic acid and anthranilic acid were tribrominated while oxine was dibrominated. In conformity with these oxidation schemes, the number of equivalents of the oxidant consumed by each of the reductants is shown in Table 1.

DCBA has been found successful for direct potentiometric and visual titrations of all the 43 reductants studied. The results (Table 1) indicate that all the titrations are sufficiently precise and accurate. DCBA excels some of the earlier developed N-halo-oxidants^{4,8}. Both solid and solution in glacial acetic acid are quite stable and the potential becomes steady quickly. More reductants can be titrated directly with DCBA than with dichloramine-T, dibromamine-T or chlorbromamine-T. Thiocyanate and Reinecke's salts which can only be determined by back-titration when these three reagents are used, can be determined directly using DCBA.

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